

High-Throughput N-Glycan Analysis in Aging and Inflammaging: State of the Art and Future Directions

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As the global population ages at an unprecedented rate, the prevalence of age-related diseases is increasing, making inflammaging – a phenomenon characterized by a chronic, low-grade inflammatory state that follows aging – a significant concern. Understanding the mechanisms of inflammaging and its impact on health is critical for developing strategies to improve the quality of life and manage health in the aging population. Despite their crucial roles in various biological processes, including immune response modulation, N-glycans, oligosaccharides covalently attached to many proteins, are often overlooked in clinical and research studies. This repeated oversight is largely due to their inherent complexity and the complexity of the analysis methods. High-throughput N-glycan analysis has emerged as a transformative tool in N-glycosylation research, enabling cost- and time-effective, detailed, and large-scale examination of N-glycan profiles.

This paper is the first to explore the application of high-throughput N-glycomics techniques to investigate the complex interplay between N-glycosylation and the immune system in aging. Technological advancements have significantly improved N-glycan detection and characterization, providing insights into age-related changes in N-glycosylation. Key findings highlight consistent shifts in immunoglobulin G (IgG) and plasma/serum glycoprotein glycosylation with age, with a pronounced rise in agalactosylated structures bound to IgG that also affect the composition of the total plasma N-glycome. These N-glycan modifications seem to be strongly associated with inflammaging and have been identified as valuable biomarkers for biological age, predictors of disease risk, and proxy biomarkers for monitoring intervention efficacy at the individual level.

Despite current challenges related to data complexity and methodological limitations, ongoing technological innovations and interdisciplinary research are expected to further advance our knowledge of glycan biology, improve diagnostic and therapeutic strategies, and promote healthier aging. The integration of glycomics with other omics approaches holds promise for a more comprehensive understanding of the aging immune system, paving the way for personalized medicine and targeted interventions to mitigate inflammaging.

In conclusion, this paper underscores the transformative impact of high-throughput N-glycan analysis in aging and inflammaging research, highlighting its critical role in the future of biomedical science.

1. Introduction

Aging is an inevitable and complex biological process characterized by a gradual decline in physiological functions and an increased susceptibility to diseases [1]. One of the critical features of aging is chronic, low-grade inflammation, a phenomenon often referred to as inflammaging [2]. This persistent inflammatory state is associated with the development of age-related diseases (ARDs), including cardiovascular diseases, neurodegenerative disorders, and metabolic syndromes [3]. Understanding the molecular mechanisms underlying aging and inflammaging is essential for developing strategies to promote healthy aging and either delay the onset or mitigate the adverse effects of ARDs, thus improving the quality of life for the elderly population and lessening the ever-increasing social and financial burden of ARDs.

Glycans, particularly N-glycans, play vital roles in numerous biological processes. N-glycans are complex carbohydrates attached to proteins, influencing their folding, stability, and consequently function. They are involved in cell-cell communication, immune responses, and protein quality control, all of which are crucial for maintaining cellular homeostasis [4]. Alterations in N-glycosylation patterns have been implicated in various pathological and physiological conditions, including many inflammatory diseases, as well as aging [5], [6]. The knowledge we have on glycans lags behind that on other macromolecules largely due to glycans' inherently complex structure which cannot be predicted from a nucleic acid sequence. This made their analysis comparatively challenging for many years, but technological advancements are rapidly closing this gap.

High-throughput N-glycan analysis, defined as the rapid testing of a large number of samples (herein considered any number of samples equal to or larger than 500), has emerged as a powerful tool in glycomics. This approach enables comprehensive profiling of glycan structures and their modifications on a large scale. Techniques such as mass spectrometry (MS), liquid chromatography (LC), capillary gel electrophoresis (CGE), and glycan microarrays have revolutionized our ability to study glycans in detail. These technologies allow for the rapid and accurate characterization of N-glycan profiles, facilitating the identification of glycan biomarkers and providing insights into the molecular mechanisms of diseases and aging [7].

This review aims to provide an overview of high-throughput N-glycan analysis techniques and their applications in aging and inflammaging research. We will touch on the roles of N-glycans, discuss the advancements and challenges in high-throughput analytical methods, and highlight significant findings from high-throughput studies. Additionally, we will examine the potential of N-glycan analysis in biological aging and aging-related disease biomarker discovery and therapeutic interventions. By integrating current knowledge and identifying gaps, this review will serve as a valuable resource for researchers and clinicians aiming to understand and leverage the role of N-glycans in aging and inflammaging.

2. N-Glycans: Structures and Functions

2.1. Structure and Synthesis of N-Glycans

N-linked glycans, also known as N-glycans, are complex carbohydrate molecules that are synthesized through the process of N-glycosylation. N-glycosylation entails the attachment of a glycan via N-acetylglucosamine (GlcNAc) to the nitrogen atom on the side chain of Asn in the protein backbone, while O-glycosylation involves glycan attachment via the oxygen atom on the side chain of Ser or Thr in the protein backbone. For glycan attachment to Asn in a protein, Asn must be present in the triad of amino acids: Asn-X-Ser or Asn-X-Thr, where X represents any amino acid except proline. Within the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) and Golgi apparatus, glycosyltransferases add, and glycosidases cleave carbohydrate structures through a series of steps that are regulated by substrate availability, enzyme concentration, ER and Golgi localization, and their activity [8].

N-glycan synthesis initiates with the transfer of a glycan precursor to the growing polypeptide chain, followed by further processing of the nascent carbohydrate-protein conjugate within the ER. Glucose residues are typically removed in this process as part of quality control. The structure then undergoes maturation in the Golgi apparatus. In eukaryotes, all N-linked glycans comprise GlcNAc β -1 bound to Asn, and they all share the same monosaccharides in the core of the glycan: Man α 1-3(Man α 1-6)Man β 1-4GlcNAc β 1-4GlcNAc β 1-Asn-X-Ser/Thr, where Man represents mannose. Subsequent monosaccharides bind to this basic structure, resulting in the three main types of N-glycans: oligomannose N-glycans (varying numbers of Man bound to the core structure), complex N-glycans (basic structure featuring one or more antennae starting with GlcNAc, galactose (Gal), fucose (Fuc), and N-acetylneuraminic acid (Neu5Ac)), and hybrid N-glycans (a combination of the previous two types, with Man extending the Man α 1-6 arm of the core and one or two GlcNAc-initiated antennae extending the Man α 1-3 arm) [8]. The antennae of complex and hybrid N-glycans can be elongated with various numbers and types of monosaccharides added, resulting in a vast array of N-glycan structures with varying degrees of complexity and diversity. They can also be truncated by a mannosidase in the Golgi, resulting in paucimannose glycans containing only three to four Man residues (Man3-4GlcNAc2) [8].

The sequence of monosaccharides in a particular glycan is not directly encoded by the genome but is instead governed by a complex interaction of genetic and environmental factors. While the genome does not explicitly specify glycan sequences, it encodes the enzymes and other proteins responsible for glycan biosynthesis. The activity of these enzymes depends on various factors, largely determined by the biochemical and physiological status of the cell, as well as the cell type [9]. Consequently, since glycans represent an integration of genetic, epigenetic, and environmental influences, they tend to be recognized as promising biomarker candidates for various complex pathological and physiological states.

2.2. Biological Roles of N-Glycans

N-glycans often play important roles in modulating the folding, stability, and function of the glycoproteins they are attached to. Upon synthesis in the ER, N-glycans serve as recognition signals for the ER quality control machinery, facilitating proper protein folding. Additionally, N-glycans can influence protein stability by shielding exposed hydrophobic regions and preventing protein aggregation [10]. Subsequent glycan processing in the Golgi results in the diversity of proteoforms that is functionally analogous to coding mutations (i.e. it changes the structure of a protein), but is inherited as a complex trait, which enables extensive inter-individual diversity without a risk to genetic heritage [11], [12].

N-glycans are involved in a multitude of biological processes, including cell-cell adhesion, immune recognition, and signal transduction [4]. For instance, N-glycans on cell surface receptors mediate ligand binding and receptor activation, thereby regulating various cellular responses, including those in the immune system [13]. Furthermore, N-glycans modulate the activity of secreted proteins, such as growth factors and cytokines, by influencing their stability, bioavailability, and receptor binding affinity, thus giving N-glycans a spotlight as key players in maintaining homeostasis circuits in multiple organ systems [13], [14], [15]. We herein focus on the immune system, whose landscape is shaped, among other factors, by N-glycans, reviewed extensively by Pinho et al. [13]. In short, their diversity and interaction potential can modify and control immune responses, ultimately promoting the resolution of inflammatory processes. Thus, when N-glycosylation is aberrant or otherwise disrupted, the delicately balanced immune homeostasis can suffer and cause persistent inflammation or autoimmunity [13].

3. High-Throughput Techniques for N-Glycan Analysis

Despite N-glycans' position as an important piece of the puzzle in physiological and pathological immune processes, the monitoring of N-glycosylation is often overlooked in clinical and immunological research. This oversight can be attributed in part to historical limitations in methodology for large-scale glycosylation analysis. However, the demand for large-scale analyses with increased statistical power has necessitated the development of high-throughput, sensitive, robust, reproducible, cost-effective, relatively straightforward, and time-efficient glycoanalytical techniques [7].

Methods that have emerged from these scientific efforts and are employed for high throughput glycoanalysis today primarily rely on LC, CGE, and MS. Additionally, lectin-based microarrays have in some cases been employed for glycan profiling. Each of these analytical methods possesses its own set of advantages and disadvantages, including glycan separation and structure determination capabilities, equipment costs, and required time and expertise. Presently, the majority of studies involving large sample sets utilize ultra-

high performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC) for total released N-glycans and LC-MS-based techniques for glycopeptide analysis.

3.1. Ultra-High Performance Liquid Chromatography (UHPLC) and Capillary Gel Electrophoresis (CGE)

The standard procedure for UHPLC and CGE analysis includes deglycosylation (i.e. enzymatic de-N-glycosylation) of proteins and subsequent labelling of released glycans to enable fluorescence detection (FLD). Compounds like 2-aminobenzamide, 2-aminoacetic acid, procainamide, InstantPC, and RapiFluor-MS are used as dyes for UHPLC, and 8-aminopyrene-1,3,6-trisulfonate acid is usually utilized for CGE. After labelling, glycans are purified using hydrophilic-interaction liquid chromatography (HILIC)-based solid-phase extraction (SPE). After this process, specific structures or structural groups of N-glycans are segregated into chromatographic or electrophoretic peaks based on their distinct retention times [7]. In UHPLC, a linear gradient is employed for glycan separation, gradually increasing the concentration of 50 or 100 mM ammonium formate in acetonitrile. In CGE, glycans are electrokinetically injected into capillaries by applying a low voltage and migrate through the capillaries under an applied electric field. While these methods offer information on the abundance of glycan peaks through fluorescence intensity measurement, they do not provide insights into the content of individual glycan peaks if used alone. Nonetheless, this approach can suffice for analyzing numerous samples, particularly in large-scale epidemiological studies involving hundreds or thousands of samples, where the content of each glycan peak can be reasonably assumed to remain constant [16], [17], [18]. While UHPLC glycan analysis offers robustness, reproducibility, and relative simplicity, making it a widely utilized method in high-throughput settings [19], CE-based methods are anticipated to emerge as the preferred choice for high-throughput IgG glycan analysis in the future. This expectation is due to their capacity for multiplexing and simultaneous analysis of up to 96 samples using multi-capillary arrays [20]. Furthermore, UHPLC can be alternatively coupled with MS, enabling the determination of glycan peak structures through fragmentation in tandem mode [21].

3.2. Mass Spectrometry (MS)

LC-MS systems have been extensively employed for high-throughput analysis of glycopeptides, most commonly subclass-specific glycopeptides of IgG [22], [23], [24] and, more recently, IgA [25]. In this approach, the chromatographic dimension is utilized to segregate glycopeptides into subclass-specific clusters primarily based on the peptide component. Subsequently, glycopeptides are separated and scrutinized in MS based on their m/z ratio. LC-ESI-MS is commonly employed for analyzing IgG glycopeptides [26]. At the same time, matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization-time of flight (MALDI-TOF-MS) is utilized for both glycopeptides and released N-glycans [27], [28], [29], [30]. To analyze at the glycopeptide level, a glycoprotein is enzymatically cleaved by trypsin and separated by reverse-phase liquid chromatography (RP-LC) based on its peptide content [26], enabling

detailed in-depth glycoprotein analysis, e.g. subclass-specific analysis of immunoglobulin glycans.

MS is also able to decipher the fine structures of glycans, including linkage types and branch points. Understanding these fine structural details, such as the distinction between different sialic acid linkages, is essential for advancing our knowledge of glycobiology, as these subtle variations can significantly impact biological processes and disease mechanisms [31], [32], [33]. Therefore, the development of high-throughput methods capable of capturing this detailed glycomics information is crucial for enabling comprehensive analysis at a systems level, paving the way for deeper insights into glycan function and regulation.

MS instrumentation and analytics are generally considered more intricate than those used for UPLC and CGE, necessitating a higher level of expertise, especially for elucidating fine structural details.

3.3. Lectin Microarrays

Lectin microarrays represent a screening method wherein a panel of lectins immobilized on a well-defined substrate enables high-throughput analysis of glycans attached to proteins or lipids [34]. The glycoprotein that is to be detected can be labelled either directly, meaning a fluorescent dye is attached to it prior to lectin binding, or indirectly, wherein a fluorescently labelled antibody specific to the glycoprotein of interest is added after lectin binding. Interaction detection is done via fluorescence detectors, allowing for very high sensitivity.

Even though lectin microarrays do not require protein digestion and/or glycan release, making them methodologically much simpler than MS, LC, and CGE-based techniques, they aren't as widely used. This is due to their relative quantitative inaccuracy compared to LC and CGE, and lack of determination of glycan compositions and structures compared to MS. Thus, lectin microarrays are mostly used for comparative analysis and are not as widely used in practice as their more quantitatively and qualitatively informative high-throughput method counterparts. That is not to say they do not still hold potential, as new perspectives in lectin-based glycan analysis are being explored via the development of droplet-based high-throughput single-cell technology that could potentially enable the simultaneous analysis of the glycome and genome in single cells. This advancement could provide new avenues for personalized medicine, specifically in the case of fighting inflammation and its adverse consequences [35].

4. Aging and Inflammaging

The definition of aging has been a topic of conversation for many years and has undergone major changes as new discoveries shed light on the molecular mechanisms causing it. Succinctly, on a macroscopic level, aging can be defined as a natural, complex process characterized by the progressive decline in physiological function and the increased

susceptibility to ARDs and geriatric syndromes (GSs) over time. It involves a variety of molecular and cellular changes that occur throughout an individual's lifespan. At the molecular level, the mechanisms causing aging can be defined as changes in the 'seven pillars of aging', namely adaptation to stress, epigenetics, inflammation, macromolecular damage, metabolism, proteostasis, and stem cell regeneration [36]. All these pillars of aging are part of an integrated network that influences each other. Notably, inflammation emerges as a central theme in aging, with the interconnected pillars all contributing to inflammaging (**Figure 1**) [37].

Inflammaging is a phenomenon characterized by chronic, low-grade inflammation that occurs in the body as people age. It is marked by an increase in pro-inflammatory markers in the bloodstream and tissues and is believed to contribute to ARDs such as cardiovascular diseases, Alzheimer's disease, diabetes, osteoporosis, and some cancers. The exact mechanisms behind inflammaging are still being studied, but it appears to result from a complex interplay of factors including continuous antigenic load and stress that trigger immune and stress responses [2], [3].

Successful aging involves decreasing chronic inflammation without compromising acute immune responses, highlighting the importance of balancing immune activity to promote healthy aging and potentially prevent or mitigate inflammaging-related disorders [38]. Although the biological background is not easy to unravel, the general consensus is that ARDs and GSs can be explained as manifestations of accelerated aging, caused by varying combinations of the same underlying mechanisms that all converge on inflammaging [39]. A particular person's genetic makeup interacting with their environment (including lifestyle effects) will guide an individual toward either accelerated or decelerated aging [37]. Some proposed approaches to curb inflammaging involve dietary interventions [40], calorie restriction mimetics like metformin [41], rapamycin [42], and acarbose [43], topical treatments to correct epidermal dysfunction as one of the factors contributing to inflammaging [44], and even extreme approaches such as voluntary parasitic worm infections [45]. Assessing the efficacy of these interventions in mitigating inflammaging is inherently challenging due to the complexity of the biological systems involved and the multifactorial nature of inflammaging.

To identify those who are at higher risk of developing ARDs and to initiate potential lifestyle or metabolic interventions as soon as possible, it is crucial to discern chronological age from biological age. One of the potential markers that could integrate the genome and environment, as well as assess the efficacy of interventions, alongside DNA methylation [46] and gut microbiota composition [47], is N-glycan profiling [48].

4.1. N-Glycan Alterations in Aging and Inflammaging

Alterations in N-glycan structures have been observed in association with both aging and inflammation, with the changes in glycosylation patterns in inflammation often resembling an acceleration of changes that normally occur during the aging process [49]. These age-

related glycan alterations can impact protein function, cellular signaling, and immune responses, potentially contributing to the pathogenesis of ARDs.

In aging, alterations in N-glycan structures have been linked to impaired protein folding and increased protein aggregation, leading to proteostasis dysfunction and cellular stress. Specifically relevant to the immune system, changes in N-glycan composition on cell surface receptors and adhesion molecules can disrupt cellular communication and immune surveillance, exacerbating age-related declines in immune function and tissue homeostasis [13]. Age-associated N-glycan changes occur in healthy aging and have also been observed in many ARDs, e.g. cardiovascular diseases [50], [51], [52], [53], Alzheimer's disease [54], [55], diabetes [56], and some cancers [57]. The biomarker potential of N-glycans in ARDs has been exhaustively reviewed by Paton et al. [58]. In a number of studies, it was shown that glycans change up to a decade before ARDs are first diagnosed [59], which suggests that they may be used as biomarkers of inflammatory processes leading to disease development and potential proxy biomarkers to evaluate the effects of both lifestyle and pharmacological interventions aimed at the reduction of disease risk.

In inflammaging, dysregulated N-glycosylation patterns have been implicated in the chronic inflammatory state characteristic of aging. Very similar N-glycan changes have been detected in both aging and inflammation in several sample types – most notably IgG, and total human plasma/serum which contains many important immune proteins that all make up its N-glycome. Alterations of N-glycans can modulate immune cell activation, cytokine production, and inflammatory signalling pathways, thereby perpetuating low-grade inflammation and contributing to the pathogenesis of age-related inflammatory diseases [49]. Balancing immune activity to support healthy, decelerated aging can thus be both reflected and impacted by glycans.

While there is no evidence that accelerated “glycan ageing” contributes to the ageing process, there is some evidence suggesting that “rejuvenation” of the IgG glycome has anti-ageing effects. For example, intravenous administration of purified immunoglobulins (IVIg) is a routinely used therapy for some inflammatory conditions and “young glycans” (those containing sialic acid) are believed to be the active component [60]. Mapping the glyco-immune landscape and understanding the functional implications of N-glycan alterations in aging and inflammaging is on the one hand essential for elucidating the underlying mechanisms of age-related pathologies and identifying potential therapeutic targets for intervention, and on the other hand potentially helpful in assessing the effectiveness of therapeutic interventions at the level of an individual. High-throughput N-glycan analysis techniques serve as cost- and time-efficient valuable tools for unravelling the complexities of glycan-mediated processes in aging and inflammaging and providing new insights into the molecular basis and potential mitigation of ARDs.

5. Applications of High-Throughput N-Glycan Analysis in Aging and Inflammaging Research

The application of high-throughput methods enables the analysis of many N-glycomes in a relatively short time, which is a major advantage in N-glycosylation analysis. Increasing the sample size helps to provide a more accurate representation of the general population due to the typically high inter-individual variability in N-glycosylation. Consequently, high-throughput N-glycan analysis has been crucial in advancing our understanding of aging and inflammaging, with many notable studies in the field employing these techniques (**Table 1**).

5.1. Plasma/Serum

The analysis of the total plasma/serum N-glycome provides information on the N-glycosylation of all glycoproteins present in plasma or serum simultaneously. Among these glycoproteins, IgG and other immunoglobulins are particularly abundant, alongside apolipoproteins and acute-phase proteins such as haptoglobin, fibrinogen, alpha-1-antitrypsin, and transferrin [61]. Alterations in glycosylation patterns of many of these proteins are linked to various pathological and physiological conditions [61]. The extensive knowledge we have about plasma/serum N-glycosylation is largely due to advancements in high-throughput methods [7] (**Table 1**).

The first high-throughput study of the total plasma N-glycome dynamics in aging was performed 15 years ago by Knežević et al. (n=1008) [62]. They demonstrated age-related changes in the abundance of some neutral plasma N-glycans, most of which likely originate from circulating IgG molecules [61]. In a study published a year later, with n=1914 individuals, they also observed a correlation between age and the levels of core-fucosylated, agalactosylated, digalactosylated, and disialylated biantennary N-glycans [63]. Also in 2010, Vanhooren et al. analysed the serum of n=594 individuals and found that the log of the ratio of two serum glycans (namely an agalactosylated fucosylated structure, FA2, and a digalactosylated fucosylated structure, FA2G2) gradually increased from the age of 40 years up until the maximum analysed age (99 years). The authors indicate that this log, called the GlycoAgeTest, could be a valuable non-invasive biomarker for general health, disease progression, and the efficacy of anti-aging interventions [64]. The following year, in a study of n=2396 individuals, Ruhaak et al. confirmed all of the correlations between the plasma N-glycome and age discovered by Knežević et al., while also correlating some N-glycan traits (specifically two chromatographic peaks whose major components are a digalactosylated structure, A2G2, and a sialylated structure, A2G1S1) to an individual's inflammatory health status. They also correlated the plasma N-glycome with healthy aging, showcasing its potential correlation to inflammaging [65].

Since then, the total plasma/serum N-glycome has been researched in a high-throughput manner in various diseases. This has established its correlation to diabetes, metabolic syndrome, medication use, autoimmune diseases, some types of cancer, etc., with its changes in inflammation often reflecting those observed in aging [6], [7], [66]. Recently, a high-throughput study conducted on n=1516 individuals further confirmed some of the serum N-glycome changes associated with age. Specifically, the levels of agalactosylated and asialylated N-glycans increased, whereas the levels of core fucosylated N-glycans

decreased with age in both sexes. When individuals were grouped into those with an “old” and a “young” serum N-glycome, the “old” group exhibited higher levels of inflammatory markers, consistent with the potential of plasma/serum N-glycome as an inflammaging biomarker [67].

Since plasma/serum contains a complex mixture of different glycoproteins, the origin of any observed change in the plasma/serum glycome is ambiguous. Such changes could be due to variations in the relative levels of proteins or glycoforms or result from a general effect that alters the glycosylation of multiple proteins [61]. Still, seeing as it is around 60% heritable [68] and the remaining plasticity can be attributed to environmental factors [62], [63], [69], it is a valid potential inflammaging biomarker.

5.2. IgG

IgG is the most abundant plasma glycoprotein and serves as the frontline defence against foreign pathogens. It consists of two light chains and two heavy chains, with both heavy chains featuring evolutionarily conserved Asn residues (Asn297) that always undergo N-glycosylation. The hinge region effectively divides IgG into two distinct domains: the Fab domain (antigen-binding fragment) and the Fc domain (crystallizable fragment). The conserved Asn297 is located within the Fc domain, and 15-20% of IgG molecules also carry N-glycans in the Fab region [70]. Due to its crucial role in the immune system and the significant impact of glycosylation on its structure and function, IgG is one of the most well-researched glycoproteins to date.

5.2.1. IgG N-glycome changes with age

Since the seminal study by Parekh et al. in 1988, which analyzed IgG N-glycosylation across different age groups (n=151 healthy individuals) and found that older individuals predominantly lacked terminal galactose residues on their IgG N-glycans [71], multiple researchers have used high-throughput techniques to confirm and expand upon these findings (**Table 1**).

The first high-throughput study of IgG N-glycans was performed in 2010 when Ruhaak and colleagues analyzed 1967 participants and found that IgG galactosylation decreases with age, replicating the results of the seminal study. They also observed an age-related increase in bisecting GlcNAc levels [72]. In 2011, Pučić and colleagues further confirmed these results and identified age as the most important predictor for IgG galactosylation levels, with 35% of the variance of IgG-G0 explained by age (n=2298) [73]. These findings were soon replicated by the same group using a different analytical method on another cohort (n=1709), with the additional finding of a decrease in IgG sialylation levels with age [74].

An in-depth analysis of larger sample size (n=5117) found that three IgG glycan peaks (GP6, GP14 and GP15, consisting mainly of one non-galactosylated glycan, FA2B, and two digalactosylated glycans, FA2G2 and FA2BG2) alone could explain up to 58% of the variance

in chronological age, significantly surpassing the predictive ability of telomeres. The remaining variance in these N-glycans was attributed to physiological parameters associated with biological age, turning the spotlight of biological age biomarkers onto IgG N-glycans [75].

Since then, the increase in IgG-G0 with age has been replicated in a Han Chinese population (n=701), confirming the findings from previous, predominantly European samples [76]. Around the same time, the only high-throughput age-association study of IgG N-glycosylation in children revealed that the direction of IgG N-glycome changes differs between adults and children. As children age, levels of agalactosylated and core fucosylated IgG N-glycans decrease, while levels of digalactosylated and bisecting GlcNAc IgG N-glycans increase, highlighting the importance of age-matched control populations in IgG glycosylation research [77].

In the largest high-throughput study to date, Štambuk et al. confirmed the age-related shift in IgG N-glycosylation (i.e. increased IgG-G0 and bisecting GlcNAc, and decreased digalactosylation levels) were largely independent of demographic factors in a sample of n=13,061 individuals. They also inferred that the age-related decline in IgG galactosylation is associated with the increase in systemic low-grade inflammation characteristic of the elderly population [78]. The analysis of IgG glycome as a tool to estimate an individual's biological age has also been developed into a commercial GlycanAge test of biological age that is available globally.

5.2.2. IgG N-glycome changes in inflammation

Age isn't the only factor that IgG N-glycosylation correlates with. While these age-related discoveries were happening, many research groups utilized high-throughput methods to analyze the impact of various other physiological parameters and states on IgG N-glycosylation. To date, IgG N-glycosylation has been researched in many autoimmune, alloimmune, infectious, cardiovascular, and inflammatory diseases, as well as in several kinds of cancers, and sex and demographic factors have been determined as important variables to control for while researching IgG glycosylation [78], [79], [80]. These efforts have led to many discoveries, revealing that major changes in IgG N-glycosylation occur in, and sometimes even precede, diagnosed disease. They have also enabled comparison of the IgG N-glycome pattern across various bodily states, consequently shedding light on the fact that the IgG N-glycosylation profile in the older population overlaps significantly with that in inflammatory diseases. Our team alone has studied IgG N-glycosylation patterns in high-throughput studies of acute systemic inflammation [81], inflammatory bowel disease [82], systemic lupus erythematosus [83], rheumatoid arthritis [84], and type II diabetes [85]. These are all illnesses with a severely imbalanced immune response, all showing modified IgG N-glycosylation patterns. Specifically, the well-established lower galactosylation levels that accompany aging, as well as lower levels of sialylation and higher levels of bisecting GlcNAc also occur during inflammation [5], [53], [84]. This is a phenomenon further confirmed via clinical markers of inflammation (C-reactive protein, low high-density

lipoprotein, and high triglycerides) [86], as well as by a recent study that correlated the premature aging and inflammation-associated comorbidities experienced by people living with HIV with an aging-related shift in IgG N-glycans [87]. In short, these studies all paved the way and continue to back the use of IgG N-glycosylation as a biomarker of inflammaging.

5.2.3. Functional implications

Since changes in IgG glycosylation have been observed and correlated with aging and aging-related inflammation, many complex and extensive functional studies have attempted to reveal the molecular mechanisms through which IgG N-glycans affect its function. This has been reviewed extensively [88], [89], [90]. Here, we will briefly discuss the effects of changes related to inflammaging – lower levels of galactosylation and sialylation and higher levels of bisecting GlcNAc. Although there is some conflicting information on the role of terminal galactose residues in IgG's effector functions [91], [92], the lack of terminal galactose on IgG N-glycans is generally considered to have a pro-inflammatory effect since it is consistently observed in inflammatory diseases up to a decade before the disease is first diagnosed. The main proposed effector mechanism involves IgG-G0's enhanced binding to the mannose-binding lectin (MBL), which initiates the lectin pathway of complement activation, thus starting the inflammatory cascade [93], [94], [95].

Regarding lower sialylation, it has been shown to promote IgG binding to type I Fc receptors, most of which are activating (FcγRI, FcγRIIa, FcγRIIc, FcγRIIIa, and FcγRIIIb) with one inhibitory exception (FcγRIIb). The role of IgG sialylation and its interplay with these receptors in the regulation of adaptive and innate immunity has been described in [96]. The consensus is that low sialylation contributes to the age-related rise in inflammation, i.e. inflammaging. Higher levels of bisecting GlcNAc bound to IgG N-glycans potentially increase antibody-dependent cellular cytotoxicity (ADCC), though the well-established pro-inflammatory effect of the loss of core fucose that naturally follows GlcNAc addition cannot be excluded in this regard [88], [97], [98], [99].

Since the glycans attached to IgG can modulate its inflammatory roles and either promote or suppress inflammation, the current consensus is that the gradual age-related shift in the IgG N-glycome is not only a sign of aging but also contributes to its acceleration (**Figure 2**) [2], [100], [101]. Thus, in a self-amplifying loop, agalactosylated IgG acts as both a “by-product” of aging and a mechanistic effector of its pathogenic changes [3], [48].

Stable in homeostasis yet highly influenced by environmental factors, easily accessible, and with high-throughput commercial analysis available, IgG N-glycosylation poses an excellent biomarker of inflammaging reflected in our biological age. The next step would be assessing whether lifestyle changes and other environmental interventions can decrease the rate of inflammaging through directed modification of the IgG glycopattern. So far, studies have been promising. For example, an anti-inflammatory shift in the IgG N-glycome has been observed following extensive weight loss [102], after eight weeks on a low-calorie diet [103],

after a period of intense physical exercise [104], and in the use of biologicals against autoimmune disease [105], [106].

5.3. Other Proteins

Aside from IgG and the total plasma proteome, there is significant potential in applying high-throughput N-glycan analysis methods to other individual proteins to study inflammaging. High-throughput platforms have recently been developed to analyze the glycosylation of transferrin [107], alpha 1-acid glycoprotein (AGP) [108], haptoglobin [109], immunoglobulin A (IgA) [25], and complement component 3 (C3) [110]. The data on the dynamics of these proteins' N-glycosylation in age is scarce due to the recency of the development of these methods. However, they hold promise, especially in the context of inflammaging, both as a means of studying the mechanisms behind it and as inflammaging biomarkers since they all play important roles in the inflammation process and can be isolated or enriched from plasma samples.

Transferrin, a negative acute phase protein whose main role is iron transfer, is one of the three individual proteins whose glycosylation dynamics with age have been researched in a high-throughput manner (**Table 1**). Contrasting the first study from 2008 using HPLC on n=1387 sera in which none of the observed age-related changes were significant [111], a study published last year utilizing a newly developed robust high-throughput method based on HILIC-UHPLC-FLD and MALDI-TOF-MS on n=1885 individuals showed significant associations with age in the majority of the detected N-glycan structures. Notably, there were changes in galactosylation levels, a steady increase in highly branched glycans, and a decrease in sialylation with age [107]. Generally, transferrin decorated with less sialic acid, called carbohydrate-deficient transferrin, is a sign of heightened inflammation and a diagnostic marker for chronic alcoholism and congenital disorders of glycosylation [112]. Replication studies on more samples are needed to realize its evident potential as an additional inflammaging marker.

AGP is an acute phase glycoprotein that comprises 45% carbohydrates in the form of five N-linked complex glycans. Aside from changing with age, its N-glycosylation also varies in various diseases, showing diagnostic and prognostic potential, though studies have mostly involved small cohorts without detailed site-specific glycan information [113], [114], [115], [116], [117], [118]. Recently, Keser et al. developed a cost-effective high-throughput site-specific N-glycosylation LC-MS analysis method for AGP. They identified changes in AGP glycosylation in individuals with hyperglycemia, indicating its potential for distinguishing those at risk of type 2 diabetes [108]. Their platform has since enabled a high-throughput study on n=803 individuals wherein a statistically significant correlation of AGP glycosylation with age was observed (**Table 1**), as well as a strong correlation with sex and multiple biochemical and physiological traits (such as BMI, triglycerides, uric acid, glucose, smoking status, etc.) [119]. Given that changes in AGP glycosylation have previously also been observed in inflammation [114], future high-throughput site-specific analyses of

multiple populations are sure to delve deeper into AGP glycosylation dynamics in inflammaging and expand upon its biomarker potential.

Haptoglobin is a positive acute phase protein with an important role in inflammation. Its four glycosylation sites and the fact that it's differentially glycosylated in various diseases (i.e. liver cirrhosis, hepatitis, pancreatitis, rheumatoid arthritis, and cancers [120]) highlights glycosylation as an important factor in haptoglobin's biology. However, its potential role in inflammaging remains unexplored. To elucidate this, a large-scale study is necessary to investigate haptoglobin's age-related N-glycosylation changes and its potential as a biomarker, a possibility that has already been recognized and discussed [121] and can be achieved utilizing the newly developed high-throughput method based on HILIC-UHPLC-FLD [109].

IgA is the most abundant antibody in the body with an important active role in initiating inflammation in many inflammatory diseases [122]. It contains two conserved Fc N-glycosylation sites [123], and its immune function is significantly influenced by its glycosylation, particularly in autoimmune diseases such as IgA nephropathy, IgA vasculitis, systemic lupus erythematosus, and rheumatoid arthritis [124]. However, the dynamics of IgA with aging have not yet been studied. This represents a promising area for future research, especially given that IgG is already an established marker of biological age and that an LC-MS-based high-throughput method to analyze IgA has recently been published [25].

As the central and most abundant protein of the complement system, C3 plays a significant role in immune surveillance and the pathogenesis of multiple diseases. A unique feature of C3 is that it is glycosylated exclusively by high-mannose N-glycans [125]. Despite limited information on the dynamics of its glycosylation in different pathophysiological states, the recently developed high-throughput LC-MS glycopeptide approach has already shown changes in C3 glycosylation in type 1 diabetes and holds promise for application to larger cohorts [110].

Aside from individual proteins, a high-throughput platform to analyze cell surface glycosylation could be very useful for discovering the dynamics of e.g. siglec (and other protein) interactions with glycans on a wider population level. This could contribute to personalized medicine and help characterize the dynamic glyco-immune landscape in aging and inflammaging.

6. Future Directions and Perspectives

The primary goal of applying high-throughput N-glycan analysis in aging and inflammaging research is to deepen our understanding of the complex interplay between N-glycosylation and the immune landscape, in particular in the context of very large inter-individual differences in protein N-glycosylation. This knowledge could facilitate the development of personalized medicine and interventions aimed at mitigating or even reversing the effects of

aging. A future direction in personalised health involves the ever-increasing employment of longitudinal sampling to establish a personal baseline. Significant progress has been made, such as revealing the N-glycome dynamics of different glycoproteins and even developing biomarkers through the analysis of extensive sample sets from diverse populations. However, substantial challenges and opportunities for further research remain, indicating there is still a long way to go [126].

The study of glycans (and glycopeptides) is inherently more challenging than e.g. protein or nucleic acid analysis due to many factors, one of which is their pronounced heterogeneity that impedes absolute quantification. To enhance the robustness and accuracy of high-throughput analyses, universal standards are already being developed and will likely come into routine use in the near future [127], [128], [129]. The focus will also be on simplifying laborious, time-consuming protocols and replacing them with deep-tech, faster and more informative methodologies. Rather than using protein digestion and glycan release as sample preparation steps, the future will involve a higher level of intact glycoprotein analysis, wherein a single affinity purification/glycoprotein enrichment step replaces the insofar utilized complex procedures. This approach has already shown vast potential as it is being used in clinical and biopharmaceuticals laboratories at present [7], [130], and could be applied routinely in intervention and health monitoring. Not yet applied in a high-throughput manner, but not without potential, is neat sample (most often serum and plasma) MS analysis which foregoes any enrichment step(s) [131].

Another challenge that occurs in high-throughput analyses is the vast amount of data produced, and data analysis is often the bottleneck of the analysis, especially in the case of MS-based methods. The application of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) to glycomics data analysis can help overcome data complexity and improve the accuracy and efficiency of glycan analysis, as well as enhance pattern recognition to better characterize the glyco-immune landscape, as well as aging and inflammaging biomarker discovery [132], [133]. Aside from including AI and ML, future interdisciplinary efforts will integrate glycomics with different omics approaches (i.e. proteomics and genomics) to comprehensively profile the immune system in aging and inflammaging, ultimately aiming to improve health outcomes [7], [134].

In summary, while high-throughput N-glycan analysis faces several challenges and limitations, its potential applications in aging and inflammaging research are vast. Continued technological advancements and methodological improvements are likely to overcome current obstacles, enabling more comprehensive and impactful studies. These developments hold promise for advancing our understanding of glycan biology, creating and implementing already existing biomarkers to improve diagnostic and therapeutic strategies, and ultimately promoting healthier aging.

7. Conclusion

High-throughput N-glycan analysis has emerged as an important tool in advancing our understanding of aging and inflammaging, utilizing large populations to uncover links between glycosylation patterns and the age-related decline in immune function. Studies consistently demonstrate age-related shifts in glycosylation patterns, particularly in IgG and total plasma/serum glycoproteins, which show promise as biomarkers for inflammaging, offering insights into biological age and disease risk beyond chronological age. The identification of specific N-glycan signatures associated with health span and disease susceptibility opens avenues for personalized medicine and targeted interventions. Understanding the glyco-immune landscape through high-throughput N-glycan analysis has profound implications for health outcomes, enabling researchers to develop strategies to mitigate inflammaging-associated diseases and promote healthier aging trajectories. Looking ahead, future research will likely focus on technological refinements to improve sensitivity, accuracy, and automation in high-throughput N-glycomics, as well as on investigating new sample types (e.g. other serum proteins involved in inflammation) and integrating glycomics with other omics approaches to unravel complex interactions within the aging immune system. Ultimately, high-throughput N-glycan analysis holds promise as a transformative tool in aging and inflammaging research, offering actionable insights for improving health outcomes in an aging population.

Author contributions:

Ana Cindrić: Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization. **Tea Pribić:** Writing - Original Draft. **Gordan Lauc:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing.

Competing Interest Statement

The authors declare the following competing financial interest(s): GL is the founder and owner of Genos Ltd, a private research organization that specializes in high-throughput glycomic analysis and has several patents in this field. AC and TP are Genos Ltd employees.

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Table 1. High-throughput studies of N-glycosylation changes with age.

study	sample number	glycoanalytical method	analyte	age range (years)	reference
total serum/plasma proteins					
Knežević et al. 2009	1008	HPLC-FLD	released glycans	18 - 93	[62]
Knežević et al. 2010	1914	HPLC-FLD	released glycans	18 - 98	[63]
Vanhooren et al. 2010	594	CGE-LIF	released glycans	3 - 99	[64]
Ruhaak et al. 2011	2396	HPLC-FLD	released glycans	30 - 80	[65]
IgG					
Ruhaak et al. 2010	1967	MALDI-MS	glycopeptides	36 - 104	[72]
Pucić et al. 2011	2298	UHPLC-FLD, MALDI-MS, LC-MS	released glycans	18 - 100	[73]
Pučić Baković et al. 2013	1709	MALDI-MS	glycopeptides	18 - 98	[74]
Krištić et al. 2014	5117	UHPLC-FLD	released glycans	17 - 97	[75]
Yu et al. 2016	701	UHPLC-FLD	released glycans	23 - 68	[76]
Pezer et al. 2016	893	LC-MS	glycopeptides	3 - 11	[77]
Plomp et al. 2017	1826	LC-MS	glycopeptides	30.2 - 79.2	[86]
Štambuk et al. 2020	13061	UHPLC-FLD, LC-MS	released glycans, glycopeptides	3 - 100	[78]
transferrin					
Trbojević-Akmačić et al. 2023	1885	UHPLC-FLD, MALDI-MS	released glycans	41 - 67	[107]
AGP					
Vučković et al. 2024	803	LC-MS	glycopeptides	18 - 88	[119]

(U)HPLC-FLD = (ultra-)high performance liquid chromatography with fluorescence detection, CGE-LIF = capillary gel electrophoresis with laser-induced fluorescence, MALDI-MS = matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization mass spectrometry, LC-MS = liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry, IgG = immunoglobulin G, AGP = alpha 1-acid glycoprotein.

Figure 1. The seven pillars of aging with inflammation as the converging point. The seven pillars of aging are: stress, epigenetics, macromolecular damage, inflammation, metabolism, proteostasis, and stem cell regeneration. The lines show their interconnectivity. In addition to being the foundational mechanisms behind aging, they all contribute to the development and progression of age-related diseases. The figure is an adaptation of “Figure 1: The seven pillars of aging” from Franceschi et al. (2018) [37].

Figure 2. The self-amplifying loop in which agalactosylated IgG is both a cause and consequence of inflammaging. Inflammaging occurs due to the accumulation of senescent and damaged cells and the molecules they secrete, as well as life-long exposure to microbial and other antigens. Both inflammation and aging are associated with agalactosylated IgG production, which in turn amplifies the chronic, sterile, low-grade, age-associated inflammation known as inflammaging. The successful reversion of the IgG N-glycosylation profile to a “younger” state through recent intervention studies reveals potential in mitigating and reversing inflammaging through targeted IgG N-glycome modification.